

A REVIEW OF SPIRITUAL WELL-BEING DURING PANDEMICS

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Abstract

An important aspect of everyday life is to develop positive relationships and genuine connection to nourish our spiritual and emotional health. Pandemic has taught us how we need to be mentally balanced to face the ongoing challenges. When Governments across the globe declared lockdown, and we were forced to sit inside our homes, the better way was knowing ourselves. Spirituality is not about religious sentiments. It is about making ourselves better by knowing oneself.

This paper intent to bring in light the way people utilised the opportunity of their lockdown period by enrolling and reading more on literatures related to spiritual wellbeing. How Universities and spiritual centres across the world has opened up free classes for mental health.

Spiritually inclined generation has enrolled themselves and motivated their inner self.

Keywords: *Spirituality, Mental wellbeing, Lockdown, Pandemic*

Introduction

Spirituality is a process of changing mindsets- mind management. Amongst many established values of spirituality is that it helps people to deal with life stressors. This has become more important as the globe has to dealt with challenges brought by the pandemic. During this time of extraordinary disruption and anxiety, Spiritual Life will be encouraging for all of us to use the coming days as an opportunity to deepen our spiritual and intellectual practices.

In the suddenly altered pace of our lives, the so called new normal, we might discover the stillness we all crave for, the stillness from which all true wisdom and justice issue. What we love rather than what we fear may come into sharper focus and just in time. That is the power of spirituality.

Review of literature

The summation of readings is categorised into three major areas of views which has formed the research gap of need of review amongst the concepts.

Novelty in approaches and administration of the COVID-19 pandemic: - Collaboration among health practitioners, religious organizations and the public is critical to the timely and effective management of the COVID-19 pandemic. There seems to be an urgent need to develop and implement programs that cater to physical, mental, and spiritual well-being. Research reveals that spirituality provides crucial support for positive mental health during worrying situations. (Neal K, 2020)

Experiences and challenges brought by the COVID-19 pandemic: - The Covid-19 pandemic significantly distorted the normal way of life and brought huge challenges to life and livelihood. However, spirituality is seen as a resource for people to deal with stress. (del Castillo,2020)

Spiritual care during the COVID-19: - Spiritual care is needed by persons struggling with the impact of the COVID-

19 pandemic. Empathy from family and friends contribute to a person's positive well-being.

Objectives

- ◆ To find the reasons behind increasing enrolment spiritual retreats
- ◆ To analyse the impact of spiritual well being

Methodology

The present study is both descriptive and analytical in nature. The study is based on secondary data. The major sources of data are from websites of J.K.Yog, Isha Foundation Amrita Vishwavidyapeetham and other prominent websites. Leading journals and periodicals and newspapers were the source of information. Information obtained from Spiritual Hotline Project, a project designed by many Brazilian healthcare workers intended to give spiritual and religious assistance to people with different cultural background has been used for an in-depth study.

Results and discussion

Declaration of pandemic and associated events has brought panic and chaos amongst people. The altered lifestyle and changed outlook and workstyle brought fear and anxiety amongst people. Above all, the daily news of death and disease has degraded the confidence in people.

Our minds are spiritually programmed since childhood. Anywhere in the world, any faith you believe, spirituality is inclined in human being. The advises of all spiritual leasers to go inside and seek within has reached to many. Several online classes and postings have boosted the spirits of many. Many joined the meditation and yoga practices and started finding peace.

i. Why people seek spiritual wellbeing?

- ◆ helps people to deal with major life stressors like anxiety, fear, loss, and death.
- ◆ spirituality has a direct link to a person's well-being.
- ◆ leads to positive psychological states of peace, healing, contentment, hope and joy.

ii. The Indian context of spirituality

Indians are spiritually inclined. the mystic music and chanting mantras are a part of Indians. The spirituality context follows: -

- Ahaar (Eating) - What we eat, how much we eat and how we eat.
- Vihaar (Relaxation) - The way in which we engage ourselves in relaxation, entertainment, and leisure time activities.
- Vichaar (Thought) - Our mental make-up, emotional control, attitude, and outlook to life.
- Vyavhaar (Action) - What we behave or practice in public and private life.

According to Indian beliefs the one who follow the spirituality context lives long strong mentally and physically.

iii. The Impact

The breakdown of pandemic has driven people to seek within. There was sudden surge seen in the visits of websites of all spiritually inclined websites all over. The admission to many universities seeking the spiritual discourse has shown an increase.

- Many of the spiritual foundations started sending spiritually inspiring quotes through social media.
- Free yoga and meditation sessions were offered by organisations LIKE J.K.Yog, Isha foundation , Rejuvenation in India

- To manage the mental well being religious classes on epics were started by ISKON.
- Several universities across the globe such as Harward, University of Northern Lowa the enrolment has increased for spiritual studies department
- Indian Univesrities such as Christ University, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University, University of Mysore, Bangalore University, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Jain Vishva Bharati Institute which offers spiritual curriculum saw an unprecedented surge for online classes.

Conclusion

For a nourishing health, we need to appreciate the importance of the body, mind, and soul and how they work together to build our overall wellbeing. A healthy body keeps you well and active. A healthy mind keeps you focused and engaged. A healthy soul keeps you fulfilled and content.

Pandemic has thrown new challenges and new lessons to the world. World has witnessed the unforeseen life-threatening evidence. Spiritual and mental wellbeing is a solution to stand strong in the time of diversity. Since March 2020, when WHO has declared covid 19 as a pandemic, there was an increase in the thoughts and practice of spiritual wellbeing. It is the right time to invest our time to be spiritually inclined for our own well being to enhance the know yourself process.

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